

Christina Destro, Maggie McGuire Kuhl, Jeanine Schulze, Laura E. Heathers, Tatiana Foroud, Thomas F. Tropea, Brittney Henry, John-Michael Talarico, Craig Stanley, Emily Flagg, Jacqueline Carley, Mandy M. Miller and the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative

INTRODUCTION

There is limited information around receiving personal research information from the perspectives of people at risk for Parkinson's disease (PD). As we plan for prevention trials, more volunteers are needed who recognize and understand their own biology. The longitudinal observational Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study is sharing research information (DAT imaging, alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay, MDS-UPDRS Part III) through its web-based myPPMI participant portal and providing remote counseling support through Indiana University. We conducted a focus group to learn more about prodromal participant viewpoints and to begin to understand the potential impact of this initiative on people at risk for PD.

METHODS

PPMI Steering Committee members created educational content on research information generally and each specific type of test. Seven prodromal participants enrolled in PPMI based on primary risk factors — 2 with REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD), 2 with hyposmia, and 3 with a PD genetic variant — participated in a focus group after reviewing the content. 57% were female; all were white. With participant consent, audio and video recordings were collected. The session transcript was utilized for a qualitative data analysis to identify key themes. Feedback from the focus group informed content revisions and prompted development of new graphics.

RESULTS

Feedback from the focus group was sorted into three categories: desire to learn information, personal and study advantages, and suggestions on how to present information. Most (5) participants wanted access to their research information with guidance on how to interpret and act on the information. All agreed the information should be shared in a digestible way and 2 participants said use of graphics would be beneficial. Five participants expressed interest in discussing their research information both with their PPMI site investigator and their personal doctor. One participant asked if they would be required to disclose their personal research information when applying for insurance.

"My Personal Research Information" page in myPPMI portal

Focus Group Demographics

Primary Risk Factor*

RBD (2) 28%

Genetic (3) 43%

Hyposmia (2) 28%

Sex

Female (4) 57%

Male (3) 43%

Family History of PD

Yes (5) 71%

No (2) 28%

Age

60-67 (2) 28%

68-75 (3) 43%

76-83 (2) 28%

*Primary risk factor is the main criterion for enrolling participants in PPMI, though they may have additional risk factors.

Category	Feedback
Desire to Learn Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Want their information (5) 71% - Brought up insurance and the cost to return results (2) 28% - Asked about more research information (e.g., cognitive) (4) 57%
Personal and Study Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May motivate, impact lifestyle decisions (2) 28% - Helps with uncertainty and planning ahead (3) 43% - Track disease trajectory over time (2) 28% - May help recruitment and retention (3) 43%
Suggestions on How to Present Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wanted study doctor to present first then could view in portal ongoing (5) 71% - Wanted personal doctor to have access (3) 43% - Clear communications: summary, plain language, graphics (7) 100%

DISCUSSION

Participants with RBD felt strongly about receiving their personal research information as soon as possible, whereas people with hyposmia were open but less enthusiastic. PPMI participants joined the study with varying levels of understanding of disease risk, and those with RBD seemed to be highly aware of their risk for developing PD.

The focus group discussion explored how the research information might impact care decisions and lifestyle choices. One participant noted his results may be the motivation he needs to add an extra workout session or make dietary changes.

CONCLUSION

The focus group identified opportunities to improve content and delivery of personal research information in PPMI. Although PPMI does not provide research data directly to personal doctors, these participants' desire for such highlights the need for broader discussion with clinicians on interpreting research data and for providing supportive services such as counseling.

Since conducting the focus group, PPMI also implemented a randomized study within myPPMI to assess the impact of returning research information in the prodromal cohort.

REFERENCES

PPMI – a public-private partnership – is funded by The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research and funding partners, including 4D Pharma, Abbvie, AcureX, Allergan, Amathus Therapeutics, Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, AskBio, Avid Radiopharmaceuticals, BIAL, BioArctic, Biogen, Biohaven, BioLegend, BlueRock Therapeutics, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Calico Labs, Capsida Biotherapeutics, Celgene, Cerevel Therapeutics, Coave Therapeutics, DaCapo Brainscience, Denali, Edmond J. Safra Foundation, Eli Lilly, Gain Therapeutics, GE HealthCare, Genentech, GSK, Golub Capital, Handl Therapeutics, Insitro, Jazz Pharmaceuticals, Johnson & Johnson Innovative Medicine, Lundbeck, Merck, Meso Scale Discovery, Mission Therapeutics, Neurocrine Biosciences, Neuron23, Neuropore, Pfizer, Piramal, Prevail Therapeutics, Roche, Sanofi, Servier, Sun Pharma Advanced Research Company, Takeda, Teva, UCB, Vanqua Bio, Verily, Voyager Therapeutics, the Weston Family Foundation and Yumanity Therapeutics.